

SECANT NEWSLETTER

Security and privacy protection in Internet of Things devices

SECANT First year activities

November / 2022

Welcome to the first SECANT Newsletter!

We are pleased to announce the publication of the first issue of the SECANT newsletter.

SECANT is a 3-year Research and Innovation Action from 2021 to 2024 funded under Horizon 2020.

It kicked off in September 2021 and it gathers a consortium of 20 partners from 10 different countries including large ICT industries, SMEs, research institutes, 1 healthcare organization and 1 EU CERT.

The healthcare sector, the sector SECANT focuses on, is a constantly increasing data-driven ecosystem populated by Internet-connected devices, shared medical databases and networks.

The interconnected nature and the high criticality of the sector makes it attractive and profitable to cyberattacks, which can range from general-purpose to highly targeted attacks.

SECANT aims to strengthen the understanding of risks, at both human and technical level and, subsequently, to enhance the digital security, privacy and personal data protection.

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PROJECT INFORMATION

SECANT: SECurity And privacy protection in IoT devices

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Overall budget: 6.567.958,75

EU contribution: 5.202.226,38

Coordinated by: NTT DATA SPAIN

STAY TUNED!

Stay updated on all our latest news, developments, research and general information regarding the SECANT project.

www.secant-project.eu

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This project has received funding from the European's Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101019645

The SECANT solution

The industrial sector is experiencing an unprecedented number of changes in recent years with new models of remote delivery, especially in complex ICT infrastructures. These advancements came with new waves of cyberattacks, raising security and privacy issues.

Meanwhile the level of security awareness is still disproportionately low compared to the criticality and potential of a security breach in critical sectors.

The healthcare sector, the sector SECANT focuses on, is a constantly increasing data-driven ecosystem populated by Internet-connected devices, shared medical databases and networks.

The interconnected nature and the high criticality of the sector makes it attractive and profitable to cyberattacks, which can range from general-purpose and often indiscriminate to highly targeted attacks utilizing advanced backdoor malware.

The limited security awareness of most healthcare professionals amplify this situation.

In such a complex cyber risk environment the SECANT Project thinks there is a need to complement traditional platform-specific and attack-specific countermeasures developed in the industry to strengthen the understanding of risks, at both human and technical level.

The human factor, which is by default the weakest link, requires intensive cybersecurity education, On the technical point, the risks need to be understood and codified in ways that can be monitored and prevented.

SECANT will do so by delivering a framework for cybersecurity risk assessment for enhancing the digital security, privacy and personal data protection in complex ICT infrastructures.

Aim

To strengthen the understanding of risks, at both human and technical level through the delivery of a holistic framework for cyber security risk assessment for enhancing the digital security, privacy, and personal data protection in complex ICT infrastructures, such in the healthcare ecosystem.

The SECANT approach

SECANT's four architectural pillars translate into different, interrelated major components

Threat Intelligence Module

Three submodules for collecting threat intelligence from SECANT supply chain stakeholders, that report this intelligence to CERT/CSIRTs and that builds dynamic taxonomies for cyber-attacks.

Cyber Security Risk Assessment Companion

CSRAC is composed of 4 modules. Using input from TIM, identifies potential vulnerabilities, assesses their propagation through the supply chain and proposes treatment solutions:

Trust & Accountability Module

TAM is based on a Distributed Ledger technology to:

- verify the integrity of data,
- establish security of devices and track provenance and integrity of their data,
- track the correct access to data.

It will verify decentralized devices identities, record devices data transactions throughout different stakeholders supply chains to ensure zero-error deliveries, and adherence to standards and auditability.

Cyber Security Training Module

The Organizational Cyber Range for security professionals to train using a simulated representation of the supply chain, modelling and emulating the complex ICT infrastructures

Security awareness training platform for other professionals and clients to familiarize themselves with best cyber security practices, using gamification strategies. It will be enhanced by a chatbot for interactive and efficient training session.

Highlight: the Human Factor in SECANT

presented by ADRESTIA R&D

In what R&D domains is ADRESTIA active?

Adrestia R&D operates mostly under the realm of cybersecurity and specifically aims to offer a thorough vulnerability assessment covering both the technical and the social aspects of ICT ecosystems.

What is the role of ADRESTIA in the SECANT consortium and who are the members involved?

Adrestia R&D is developing the Human Vulnerability Assessment and Technical Vulnerability and Impact Assessment solutions under SECANT's scope. Kapouranis Dimitrios and Konstantinos Kyriakou are responsible for the design and development of each of the solutions, respectively.

Can you explain what is the objective of the CyberSecurity Risk assessment companion?

The Cyber Security Risk Assessment Companion (CSRAC) will provide the necessary tools to monitor all the entities involved in a network and apply the security controls according to the criticality of the data and services offered by each of them through different levels of monitoring.

Under this CSRAC's scope the Human Vulnerability Assessment (HVA) will assist in the assessment of the personnel while the Technical Vulnerability and Impact Assessment (TVIA) will aid in the immunisation of the technical assets of an ICT ecosystem in an attempt to provide a more accurate and complete vulnerability assessment.

The SECANT use cases

The SECANT platform will be validated through four different Pilot Use Cases:

Pilot Use Case 1

to validate SECANT's ability to improve transportation safety and ensure zero-error delivery of patients transported using time-constraint Emergency Medical Services.

Pilot Use Case 2

to validate SECANT's efficiency to deal with cascading effects of cyber threats and with propagated vulnerabilities in connected healthcare infrastructures, as well as in remote healthcare settings.

Pilot Use Case 3

to validate the capabilities of SECANT to ensure privacy, data protection and accountability when operational data is being exchanged within the healthcare supply chain.

Pilot Use Case 4

to validate the capabilities of SECANT's cyber security training modules and critical infrastructure cyber range.

Market analysis

The **cybersecurity market worldwide** is experiencing a significant growth and this expansion can be attributed to the continuous digitization of businesses which in turn rises the incidence of cyber-attacks¹.

This danger pushes companies towards the adoption of advanced cybersecurity solutions in order to secure every part of the infrastructure from cyberattacks. Additionally, regulations regarding the privacy of user data, such as EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), is further accelerating the adoption of cybersecurity solutions by the enterprises and thus, the market is expected to grow in the upcoming years.

Other factors that positively affect the market growth is the rise in malware and phishing threats among enterprises along with the fast adoption of cloud-based services². Cloud and mobile services utilize digital transactions which can be targets to malevolent attackers through the exploitation of a wide range of cybersecurity gaps.

COVID-19 had a strong **impact** not only on economical and societal domains but also on the business sector. During the pandemic, professionals were encouraged to work from home and thus, digital technology became more important in employees' new working environment.

This is one of many factors which cumulatively increased the rate of cyberattacks especially targeting video conferences or focusing on users via phishing scams. To put things into perspective, between February and May 2020 more than 500.000 people were affected by cybersecurity breaches worldwide³.

This has also affected the companies expenses and losses since a total of 101 Billion records is estimated to have been lost by organized threat actors.

2020 was record breaking for record compromises

As a consequence, the already growing cybersecurity market rose even more in popularity since people aspired to ensure data security and protect user privacy. Forecasts indicate that the global cybersecurity market is expected to be worth USD 266.6 Billion by 2027⁴, thus depicting an annual growth rate of 8.9%.

In the EU region, the cybersecurity market is growing with even faster rate. More specifically, the market is projected to reach USD 40 Billion in 2022. The total revenue is expected to show an annual growth rate of 12.54% between the period 2022-2027, resulting in a market volume of USD 73.35 Billion by 2027⁵.

During COVID-19 the healthcare sector had become a primary target of cybersecurity attacks. This situation combined with the enormous pressure to deliver health care in order to save lives, placed healthcare in a vulnerable situation. As a result, there was a large increase in cybersecurity solutions that were provided to hospitals, clinics, doctors and healthcare in general in order to alleviate the risk of cyber threats.

Healthcare sector enjoys a large forecasted growth and is expected to outgrow Banking, financial services and insurance (BFSI) by 2030. More specifically, the **global cybersecurity market in healthcare** was valued at USD 12.6 Billion in 2021 and is forecasted to expand at an annual growth rate of 18.3% from 2022 to 2030⁶. This presents new players with an immense opportunity to deliver new services and products in a landscape that offers and will continue to offer good opportunities.

- <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/4858296/global-cybersecurity-market-forecasts-from-2019>
- <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/cyber-security-market>
- <https://www2.deloitte.com/ch/en/pages/risk/articles/impact-covid-cybersecurity.html>
- <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/cyber-security-market-505.html>
- <https://www.statista.com/outlook/tmo/cybersecurity/europe#revenue>
- <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/cyber-security-market>

SECANT events

Panel: SSI in healthcare: from devices to individuals, challenges and opportunities

May 17

IOTA organized a **panel discussion** on SSI in healthcare at the European identity and cloud conference. SECANT was represented by UBITECH, NTTDATA and IOTA.

SECANT participated in a joint **clustering webinar** on with projects funded under the H2020 SU-DS02 and H2020-SU-DS03 topics to explore possible collaborations between EU funded projects relevant to Cybersecurity, Personal data protection and GDPR compliance topics.

May 11

Clustering Webinar on Security, Privacy and Data Protection

Invited projects under H2020-SU-DS02 and SU-DS03 topics

May 25

The SECANT project was represented by IANUS consulting in a workshop organised by EIGHT BELLS Ltd. The **Workshop** focused on exploring the State of the Art related to ICT, covering aspects such as 5G/6G, Cybersecurity, IoT and Cloud.

Participation with a SECANT project presentation by CERTH as Scientific and Technical Manager in the workshop organized in the IoTWeek 2022, entitled "**Safer and more Connected: IoT Security & Data Protection**" and coordinated by the ERATOSTHENES and ARCADIAN-IoT project.

June 22

July 1

The SECANT project took part in the **Projects to Policy Seminar** organized by the European Research Executive Agency from 30th June to 1st of July in Brussels. The event aimed at framing some of the key challenges in the policy, and cybersecurity areas of the European Union

In July, Karolinska Institutet's researcher (Sokratis Nifakos), presented a conference paper "ICT in Healthcare: the role of IoT and the SECANT solution" in the 2022 **IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience**.

July 27

October 28

Monica Caballero (NTTDATA), the project coordinator, represented SECANT in a **National Cybersecurity conference** organised by SECANT partner DNSC.

In the next SECANT newsletter

1st face to face plenary meeting

In January 2023, the first face to face plenary meeting will take place in the Project Coordination's hometown, Barcelona, where the consortium partners will finally meet for the first time and the SECANT first results will be presented.

Cybersecurity webinar

In 19th January 2023, SECANT will participate in a cybersecurity webinar organized by CitySCAPE that intends to discuss topics such as GDPR and data handling, Security assurance, NIS directive and contribution to standards. SENTINEL, HEIR, TRAPEZE and ECORRIDOR are also confirmed participants.

SENTINEL

TRAPEZE

HEIR

E-CORRIDOR

CitySCAPE

Cybersecurity conference (organized by ELECTRON)

ELECTRON is organizing an International Event on Energy Crisis and Cybersecurity from 5 to 7 of December 2022 in Baku, Azerbaijan.

Major international organisations and energy industry representatives will be invited to present their initiatives and invite participants to take actively part at their initiatives.

Above that, prominent representatives of energy and cybersecurity scientific sector, representatives from business investing in the energy and members of the European Commission, responsible for energy policy, are going to attend and participate physically or remotely.

You can find more information and the registration form in the following link:

<https://electron-project.eu/electron-international-event/>

The SECANT consortium

3 Large ICT industries

NTT DATA

THALES
Building a future we can all trust

SIMAVI
Software Imagination & Vision

9 SMEs

Ei8HTBELLS
Independent Research & Consultancy

UBITECH
ubiquitous solutions

axon logic

**INFO
LYSIS**

**ianus
consulting**

EXALENS®

**Security Labs
Consulting**

Adrestia
Equilibrium In Research & Development

bi2S Ltd
Business and IoT
Integrated Solutions

5 research institutes and universities

**Karolinska
Institutet**

i2cat

iti Information
Technologies
Institute

**TIC
Salut Social**

**UNIVERSITY OF
SURREY**

1 healthcare organization

**POLARIS
Medical**

1 European CERT

**CENTRUL NAȚIONAL DE RĂSPUNS LA INCIDENTE
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